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CARBON FOOTPRINT ANALYSIS OF THE DISTRIBUTION OF CHEESE COASTAL FROM THE COLOMBIAN CARIBBEAN USING QGIS'S ONLINE ROUTING MAPPER

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Abstract: *In supply chains, the logistics and distribution process is crucial, especially in assessing environmental impacts such as the carbon footprint. Therefore, this study comprehensively analyzes the carbon footprint of the distribution of Costeño cheese from the Colombian Caribbean region, using the QGIS Online Routing Mapper plugin and the "Here Routing API" online server. Geospatial tools were used to visualize optimal distribution routes, and a calculation methodology was developed based on distance, vehicle type, and fuel. The results highlight notable disparities between departments, identifying the department of La Guajira between Magdalena and Córdoba as the largest emitter, and certain municipalities within it—such as Uribia, Manaure, and Dibulla—as significant contributors to the total carbon footprint, given the great distances required to reach the destination market. It concludes by highlighting the need to address sustainability in transport and proposes the creation and formalization of associations of artisanal cheese producers and the establishment of collection centers, which allow the production to be aggregated in a centralized manner, facilitating the availability of products in the supply chain as a key strategy to reduce carbon emissions per producer and improve efficiency in the distribution of Queso Costeño del Caribe Colombiano.*

Keywords: *Carbon Footprint, Caribbean Coastal Cheese Distribution, QGIS, Sustainability.*

INTRODUCTION

This study presents the methods used to estimate CO₂ emissions generated during the transportation of Colombian Queso Costeño del Caribe (Caribbean Coastal Cheese), from producers to potential customers. Quantifying the main sources of greenhouse gas emissions in the Queso Costeño del Caribe supply chain represents a fundamental step toward sustainability. Ultimately, the purpose of this academic-scientific exercise is to chart a path toward more sustainable agri-food production and distribution, with the conviction of significantly contributing to efforts to measure CO₂ emissions in the agri-food transportation sector in Colombia.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Principle of sustainability

Sustainable development is based on one essential principle: meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs [1]-[3]. This definition, formulated by the World Commission on Environment and Development in the 1987 Brundtland Report, underlines the need to balance current progress with the conservation of resources and the environment for future generations [4], [5]. Therefore, integrating accurate CO₂ measurements into supply chain distribution optimization models for goods and services not only aligns with principles of environmental responsibility, but also offers tangible benefits for businesses, consumers, and the productive sectors. Sustainability Science, recognizing the complexity of interconnected challenges, advocates for holistic approaches [6]. By measuring and accounting for CO₂ emissions in logistics optimization models, companies can make informed decisions that minimize the environmental

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impact of their distribution operations; This not only contributes to climate change mitigation but also positions companies at the forefront of sustainable business practices, responding to market expectations and strengthening their commitment to equitable and environmentally friendly development [7].

Carbon Footprint Concept

Measuring the carbon footprint, according to the Greenhouse Gas Protocol (GHG), is of fundamental importance in environmental management and the evaluation of mitigation strategies [2], [8]. The carbon footprint is an indicator that measures GHG emissions, in this case, in the productive sector [3], [9]. In this sense, the definition of GHGs, as established in the Kyoto Protocol in 1997, is adopted: a permanent layer in the middle of the atmosphere that prevents all solar radiation returned by the Earth from escaping, thereby causing an increase in temperature beneath this layer [4], [10] – [11].

Greenhouse gases (GHG) are substances present in the atmosphere, both of natural and human origin, that contribute to the greenhouse effect. This effect implies that the gases absorb thermal radiation and emit it in all directions, generating a warming of the Earth's surface [12]. The constant emission of these gases leads to an increase in global warming, negatively affecting climate change. The influence of GHGs on this change depends on their concentration, permanence in the atmosphere and their impact on global temperature. The scientific community agrees that the continuous emission of these gases, without major efforts, would cause significant warming and irreversible changes in the population and ecosystems; given that CO₂ is one of the most impactful GHGs in the Earth's atmosphere [5], [13].

Global Impact

By quantifying GHG emissions, the main sources of pollution can be clearly identified according to the type of gas emitted, thus facilitating the design and implementation of policies and measures that reduce their impact on the environment, especially in productive development. Therefore, GHG management is presented as a powerful tool for mitigation, control, and encouragement for the adoption of proactive strategies to achieve organizational sustainability and, consequently, for the planet [6], [14] - [15]. However, implementing overly strict policies, norms, or regulations can harm the interests of productive governments, discourage their management, and skew the benefits to only certain sectors and/or social segments [7], [16].

Globally, the sectors that contribute most to CO₂ emissions are electricity generation with 40.1%, transportation with 24.7%, industry with 20.1%, construction with 7.7%, and the remaining sectors with 7.4% [5], [17].

Regarding the percentage of CO₂ emissions in the transport sector at the national level in the last decade, the main sources of emissions are in the national freight transport mode such as road and river, representing more than 70% and 22-28%, respectively, while other modes of transport do not reach 3% [8], [18].

Among the environmental objectives of the Colombian government is the reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the transportation sector. This requires the commitment and cooperation of key stakeholders in this productive sector. This commitment proposes a Level 3 scenario, where, according to the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development, it is estimated that by 2050, emissions generated by interurban freight transported by road will reach 54% by rail 41%, and by river 5% [9], [17]. In addition, the fact that gasoline-based truck vehicles comprise 35% of urban areas and 9% of interurban areas is being studied. Diesel-based truck vehicles comprise 60% of urban areas and 90% of interurban areas; in addition, compressed natural gas (CNG) truck vehicles comprise

5% of urban areas and 1% of interurban areas. Finally, truck-type vehicles based on Liquefied Natural Gas - LNG are composed of 0% urban and 0% interurban [10], [19].

Supply chains of goods and services have become fundamental to the economic development of every locality, region, and country. A detailed understanding of the structure and operation of supply chains offers valuable insight into the identification of the key activities that comprise the chain, as well as the potential impacts they generate [5], [8], [20] – [21]. In this context, transportation serves as a fundamental axis for economic integration; but unfortunately, it also serves as a significant source of pollution because of GHGs [11], [22].

Colombia recognizes greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from freight transport, particularly highlighting the problems in the road subsector, characterized by poor decisions and intense competition. This has led to low profits and an obsolete fleet with high emissions; therefore, it advocates for interventions that do not penalize the activity, but rather offer incentives and financial flexibility, facilitating the exploration and implementation of new technologies as an opportunity to reduce emissions and improve efficiency in the sector [12], [23].

Percentage of CO₂ emissions nationwide

In the last decade, the main sources of domestic freight transportation in Colombia have been road and river transport, representing more than 70% and 22-30%, respectively, while other modes of transportation do not reach 3% [4], [9].

The Colombian national government aims to minimize Green House Gases (GHG) emissions in the transportation sector in Colombia, which requires the commitment and cooperation of key stakeholders. This commitment proposes a Tier 3 scenario, where, according to the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development, it is estimated that by 2050, emissions generated by interurban freight transported by road should be 54%, by rail 41%, and by river 5% [9], [24]. In addition, it has been studied that gasoline-based truck vehicles are composed of 35% of urban and 9% interurban vehicles. Diesel-based truck vehicles are composed of 60% urban and 90% interurban vehicles. CNG-based truck vehicles are composed of 5% urban and 1% interurban vehicles. Finally, LNG-based truck-type vehicles are composed of 0% urban and 0% interurban [10], [25].

Supply chains for goods and services have become fundamental to the economic development of each country. A detailed understanding of the structure and operation of supply chains offers valuable insight into the identification of the key activities that comprise them [5] and [8]. In this context, transportation serves as the main axis for economic integration; but unfortunately, it also serves as a significant source of pollution due to the generation of GHGs [11], [26].

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

The geographic area of interest for the research project "Strengthening the productive and commercial capacity of the Coastal Cheese supply chain in the Colombian Caribbean subregions, departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira" offers a series of benefits from interaction with 27 municipalities, 9 in each department, in equal proportions. The departments are Magdalena, Córdoba,

and La Guajira, each of which has a footprint in 9 municipalities per department, in the northern, central, and southern subregions of each of these (see Figure 1).

To have quantitative data that would allow the research project and this article to perform the required calculations and analyses, the following methodological process was developed to generate specific parameters and incorporate them into the distribution optimization model for Queso Costeño del Caribe Colombiano. The method applied to calculate CO₂ is the application of geospatial tools to visually represent the routes and the amount of CO₂ that could be generated if said route were used.

Figure 1. Project study area. Source: Project "Strengthening the productive and commercial capacity of the Coastal Cheese supply chain in the Colombian Caribbean Subregions, departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, La Guajira".

The methodology was developed in three key stages:

- a. First, detailed information was collected on the locations of Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese producers, and the key vehicle types used to transport the product of interest, which in this case is Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese, were identified.
- b. Second, the QGIS "Online Routing Mapper" plugin was used to plot and map the routes interactively and accurately.
- c. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions were calculated for the distribution process of Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese. This calculation was based on the distances traveled from the producer to each target city for marketing and the type of vehicle to be considered due to the type of fuel used.

a. Source and destination locations for CO2 calculation

For this study, the locations of 101 producers from 27 municipalities were considered. The municipalities of the Magdalena department are: El Banco, Guamal, Santa Ana, Plato, Nueva Granada, Ariguaní, Fundación, Pivijay, and Ciénaga. The municipalities of the Córdoba department are: Montelíbano, Planeta Rica, Sahagún, Montería, Los córdobas, Puerto Escondido, Pueblo Nuevo, Chinú, and San Antero. The municipalities of the La Guajira department are: Villanueva, San Juan del Cesar, Hatonuevo, Riohacha, Dibulla, Manaure, Uribia, Maicao, and Urumita.

The key destinations for the marketing of Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese were 11 target cities; the demand for Caribbean Coastal Cheese is particularly high in the cities of Santa Marta, Riohacha, Monteria, Barranquilla, Bogotá, Bucaramanga, Cartagena, Cali, Cúcuta, Medellín, and Pereira.

b. Designing distribution routes using QGIS's ONLINE ROUTING MAPPER

QGIS software is essential for mapping and visualizing production movements throughout the supply chain of Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese. This graphical tool clearly represents the interconnection between production, distribution, and consumption points, facilitating the identification of areas for improvement in terms of production efficiency and sustainability.

But what is QGIS ONLINE ROUTING MAPPER? It's a plugin that uses online mapping services to perform interactive and accurate route analysis. It helps plan and optimize transportation and logistics by showing the shortest and most efficient routes between different points. It's an innovative and effective solution that combines online mapping technology with the analytical power of QGIS.

To generate optimal routes from producers to destination cities using QGIS software, it is essential to load the base layers that include the origin points, represented by the producer locations, and the destination points, which correspond to potential customer cities for marketing. The necessary plugin is then installed from the "Plugins" menu in QGIS, by accessing the Plugin Manager and selecting the installation option.

Once the plugin is installed, its parameters are configured, adjusting them according to the type of route and the mode of transport of interest. In this case, the "Online Service" and "HERE Routing API" options were selected to generate the shortest route (see Figure 2). The route's start and end points are then selected on the map, either using the QGIS selection tools or by directly entering the geographic coordinates (see Figure 3).

Additional information is then added to the route, including the producer's name and destination cities. Function configuration in the field calculator is crucial in this step, and a virtual field is created and assigned a specific name.

Figure 2: Configuring Online Service Options
Source: QGIS software graphical interface

Figure 3: Selecting the origin and destination points
Source: QGIS software graphical interface

The field calculator is used to calculate the route of the line layer, using the geometric function \$length to obtain the total length of the line. Dividing this value by 1,000 gives the distance in kilometers of the route generated by the plugin. This allows us to calculate the distance traveled from the producer to the destination customer. This approach, integrated into QGIS, provides an effective solution for analyzing and visualizing optimal routes in a geospatial context.

c. Calculation of CO2 Estimates

Internal combustion engines (ICEs), particularly diesel engines, are widely used as a driving force in industrial applications such as transportation, agriculture, and power generation [13]. Diesel engines compress air to very high pressures and temperatures, such that fuel injections can generate high levels of carbon monoxide (CO) or CO₂ [14]. Therefore, market competition has forced organizations to evolve, allowing them to adapt to the dynamic conditions of these markets [6].

To determine the conversion factor for CO₂ generated per kilometer traveled from the point of origin to the destination point, equation (1) is used

$$ECO2_{ij} = \rho_{C12H23} \cdot e_{C12H23} \cdot d_{ij} \cdot p_{CO2} \quad (1)$$

Where: $ECO2_{ij}$ represents the amount of CO₂ emissions in kilograms (kg) from producer i to customer j , ρ_{C12H23} is the density of diesel in kilograms per liter (Kg/L), e_{C12H23} V represents the efficiency of diesel in liters per kilometer traveled (L/Km), d_{ij} is the distance traveled in kilometers (km) from producer i to customer j , and, p_{CO2} is the ratio of CO₂ in kilograms present in one liter of diesel.

Since one of the fundamental objectives of this study is to calculate the amount of CO₂ generated in the distribution process of Caribe coastal cheese, it is essential to accurately estimate these emissions per kilometer traveled. To achieve this, it is imperative to determine an effective conversion factor. The density of Diesel is around 0.84 Kg/L and 0.832 Kg/L, which on average would be 0.836 Kg/L [15], [16].

To estimate fuel efficiency per km traveled, the equation was defined (2):

$$e_{C12H23} = \frac{V}{x} \quad (2)$$

Where V represents the volume of Diesel fuel used and x represents the amount traveled. In the specific case of truck type vehicles, with a maximum load capacity of 9 tons, the average Diesel consumption, its efficiency is 100 kilometers for every 5 gallons, where one gallon is equivalent to 3.786 L to 3.785 L, so what on average would be 3.7855L [17] – [20].

$$e_{C12H23} = \frac{5 \text{ galones}}{100 \text{ Km}} \cdot \frac{3,7855 \text{ L}}{1 \text{ galón}} = \frac{18,9275 \text{ L}}{100 \text{ Km}}$$

$$e_{C12H23} = 0,189275 \frac{\text{L}}{\text{Km}}$$

To determine the percentage of CO₂ from engine combustion, the chemical formula of Diesel is considered: C₁₂H₂₃ [21], since when reacting with oxygen (O₂) with heat, combustion is generated and as a result CO₂, water (H₂O) and energy are obtained, so we can express the chemical reaction in equation (3) [22]. By balancing the previous equation, we obtain equation (4).

Dividing the amount of CO₂ by the amount of C₁₂H₂₃ fuel, we obtain that a liter of Diesel has a ratio of 3,1567 de CO₂.

$$p_{CO2} = 3,1567$$

Clearing the determined values $\rho_{C12H23} = 0.836 \text{ Kg/L}$, $e_{C12H23} = 0,189275 \text{ L/Km}$, $p_{CO2} = 2,1567$ For (1) equation (5) is obtained, with which the amount of CO₂ generated in Kg per Km traveled will be estimated based on the previous calculation of the distances of the routes in stage 2 with the ONLINE ROUTING MAPPER tool of QGIS.

$$ECO2_{ij} = 0,836 \text{ Kg/L} \cdot 0,189275 \text{ L/Km} \cdot d_{ij} \cdot 3,1567$$

$$ECO2_{ij} = 0,4995 \text{ Kg/Km} \cdot d_{ij} \quad (5)$$

RESULTS

The results derived from the implementation of the proposed method have played a crucial role in the development of the map that traces the distribution routes of the Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese supply chain (see Figure 4). This map is visually representative and is displayed in Figure 4, offering a graphic view of the intricate distribution network of this product. In this diagram, the green dots symbolize the point of origin of each route, corresponding to the 101 Caribbean Coastal Cheese producers identified within the framework of the research project. These producers constitute the primary link in the production of the product and represent the initial point of the supply chain.

In contrast, the red dots on the map indicate the final destinations of each route, highlighting the 11 potential cities where Queso Costeño Caribe is projected to be distributed. These cities have been strategically identified as favorable markets for the product, based on historical consumption data detailed by the National Department of Statistics (DANE). The white lines interspersed with black stripes on the map illustrate the most efficient routes for the distribution of Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese. These routes were determined based on the proposed method, which seeks to optimize supply chain efficiency by minimizing transportation distances. Consequently, the results achieved through the application of the proposed method have enabled the practical mapping of distribution routes; they have also provided a very useful tool for planning and effective management of the supply chain of Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese.

Figure 4: Distribution route of Caribbean Coastal Cheese from origin and destination points.

Source: Project "Strengthening the productive and commercial capacity of the Coastal Cheese supply chain in the Colombian Caribbean subregions, departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira."

The results on CO₂ emissions reveal significant disparities between the departments of La Guajira, Córdoba, and Magdalena (see Figure 5). According to estimates, La Guajira tops the list with a significant figure of 185,401.91 kg of CO₂, contrasting sharply with the approximate 77,858.06 kg and 68,327.60 kg of CO₂ recorded in the departments of Córdoba and Magdalena, respectively.

The frequency histogram for each detailed municipality provides a clear representation of CO2 emissions, highlighting certain municipalities as significant contributors to the total carbon footprint (see Figure 6). Uribia, Manaure, and Dibulla stand out as the main emitters, with specific estimates of 57,115.33 kg, 34,435.53 kg, and 28,856.12 kg of CO2, respectively.

Figure 5: Frequency histogram of total emissions from the Caribbean Coastal Cheese distribution route at origin and destination points for the departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira. Source: Project "Strengthening the productive and commercial capacity of the Coastal Cheese supply chain in the subregions of the Colombian Caribbean, departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira."

Figure 6: Frequency histogram of total emissions from the Caribbean Coastal Cheese distribution route from the origin and destination points for the municipalities of the departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira. Source: Project "Strengthening the productive and commercial capacity of the Coastal Cheese supply chain in the subregions of the Colombian Caribbean, departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira."

The frequency histogram with error bars shows significant disparities in CO₂ emissions between the departments of Córdoba, La Guajira, and Magdalena (see Figure 7). Córdoba shows an average of 262.15 kg of CO₂, being the lowest, while La Guajira leads with 330.48 kg of CO₂, indicating a higher average contribution. Magdalena is in the middle, with an average of 270.70 kg of CO₂. These values provide a comprehensive view of the regional carbon footprint, represented by a weighted average of 298.46 kg of CO₂. Furthermore, the standard deviations reveal the variability in emissions, with La Guajira being the most notable with 181.66 kg of CO₂, followed by Magdalena with 145.69 kg of CO₂, and Córdoba with 121.28 kg of CO₂. Analyzing these data not only highlights the importance of addressing average emissions in each department, but also the need to understand and manage variability in emission sources to develop adaptive and effective strategies at the regional level.

Figure 7: Frequency histogram of average emissions from the Caribbean Coastal Cheese distribution route at origin and destination points for the departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira. Source: Project "Strengthening the productive and commercial capacity of the Coastal Cheese supply chain in the subregions of the Colombian Caribbean, departments of Magdalena, Córdoba, and La Guajira".

CONCLUSIONS

This study on CO₂ emissions in the Caribbean Coastal Cheese supply chain has provided valuable results that highlight the importance of addressing sustainability in freight transportation, specifically in food products. Therefore, the estimated measurement of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is essential for environmental management, improving competitiveness, and formulating mitigation strategies that contribute to sustainable development.

The implementation of geospatial tools, in conjunction with GHG emissions calculation methodologies and techniques, has made it possible to visualize the optimal distribution routes for a food product, identifying the number of emissions that can be generated by the transportation route from the producer of origin to the destination of the potential customer. This makes it possible to internalize potential environmental impacts on the surrounding environment in the production process. The results reveal significant disparities between the departments studied, with La Guajira standing out as the largest emitter of CO₂ due to its remoteness and the large number of small producers scattered throughout the department. In addition, certain municipalities, such as Uribia, Manaure, and Dibulla, stand out as significant contributors to the total carbon footprint.

The analysis of averages and standard deviations applied in this case provides a deeper understanding of the variability in emissions. La Guajira leads with the highest average, indicating a higher contribution compared to Córdoba and Magdalena.

At the global level, the study highlights the crucial role of the freight transport sector, which is responsible for a significant portion of CO₂ emissions.

An effective strategy for reducing the number of emissions generated by each producer is to establish partnerships, enabling agglomerations at collection centers for larger quantities of products and optimizing the number of trips and cargo transported, both for inputs and goods, throughout the supply chain. This will allow for the implementation of a better distribution model that facilitates an increase in the volume of cargo transported with fewer routes for Colombian Caribbean Coastal Cheese, thereby reducing the number of GHG emissions per shipment of the final product to each potential customer.

In conclusion, this study not only contributes to the understanding of CO₂ emissions in the Caribbean Coastal Cheese supply chain, but also provides a solid basis for informed decision-making, promoting sustainable business practices and helping to meet emissions measurement targets in the Colombian food freight transport sector and the fulfillment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

RECOMMENDATIONS

The disparities found between departments underscores the importance of optimizing distribution routes. Future research could explore technological solutions and logistics strategies to reduce transportation distances by creating collection centers, thereby reducing the distances and number of distribution routes from the collection center to the final customer and, consequently, the associated emissions. Given the importance of the freight transport sector in CO₂ emissions, it is suggested to foster collaboration between key stakeholders, such as producers, transporters, and government authorities. Finally, the creation of cross-sector associations and a cheesemaking federation can facilitate the implementation of effective strategies and the achievement of shared goals.

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CONTRIBUTION OF THE AUTHORS

Edwin Causado Rodriguez worked on the methodological process of calculating the carbon footprint in the distribution of coastal cheese from the Colombian Caribbean, applying the Online Routing Edwin Mapper plugin for QGIS and an online server called "Here Routing API". Andres Peñaloza Fernandez and Johana Fonseca Tovar collected and analyzed data and applied geospatial tools to visualize optimal distribution routes. The three authors contributed to the interpretation of the results and to the preparation and writing of the document.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to the publication of this manuscript. Additionally, ethical aspects, including plagiarism, informed consent, data fabrication and/or falsehood, duplicate, and redundant publication were observed and verified by the authors.

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